

THE ROLE OF DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES IN MODERN EDUCATION

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Abstract: This article examines the increasing role and impact of digital technologies on the education system in Uzbekistan. It reviews the current state of technology integration in Uzbek schools and universities, and analyzes both the benefits and challenges of this digital transformation. The article discusses how digital tools are reshaping teaching and learning, expanding access to educational resources, facilitating personalized and adaptive learning, fostering 21st century skills, and more.

Keywords: digital technology, education, e-learning, ICT in education, digital pedagogy, Uzbekistan

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada O'zbekistonda raqamli texnologiyalarning ta'lim tizimiga ta'siri va roli tobora ortib borayotgani ko'rib chiqiladi. U O'zbekiston maktablari va universitetlarida texnologiyalar integratsiyasining hozirgi holatini ko'rib chiqadi, shuningdek, ushbu raqamli transformatsiyaning afzalliklari va muammolarini tahlil qiladi. Maqolada raqamli vositalar o'qitish va o'rganishni qanday o'zgartirishi, ta'lim resurslaridan foydalanish imkoniyatini oshirishi, shaxsiylashtirilgan va moslashuvchan o'rganishga hissa qo'shishi, 21-asr ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirishi va boshqalar muhokama qilinadi.

Kalit so'zlar: raqamli texnologiyalar, ta'lim, elektron ta'lim, ta'limdagi AKT, raqamli pedagogika, O'zbekiston

Аннотация: В этой статье рассматривается возрастающая роль и влияние цифровых технологий на систему образования в Узбекистане. В ней рассматривается текущее состояние интеграции технологий в школах и университетах Узбекистана, а также анализируются как преимущества, так и проблемы, связанные с этой цифровой трансформацией. В статье обсуждается, как цифровые инструменты меняют преподавание и обучение, расширяют доступ к образовательным ресурсам, способствуют персонализированному и адаптивному обучению, развивают навыки 21 века и многое другое.

Ключевые слова: цифровые технологии, образование, электронное обучение, ИКТ в образовании, цифровая педагогика, Узбекистан

INTRODUCTION

The rapid advancement and proliferation of digital technologies is dramatically reshaping all aspects of society, including the education sector. This digital transformation of education refers to the integration of digital tools, platforms, content and practices into teaching, learning and education management, from early childhood education through university. In Uzbekistan, as in countries worldwide, there is growing recognition of the potential for digital technologies to expand access to quality education, improve teaching and learning outcomes, foster innovation and 21st century skills, and drive socio-economic development [1].

However, the impact of digital technologies on education in Uzbekistan has not been comprehensively studied. This article aims to examine the current landscape of digital education in Uzbekistan, assess the benefits and challenges, and offer policy recommendations to leverage digital technologies to improve educational quality, equity and efficiency.

METHODS AND LITERATURE REVIEW

To assess the role and impact of digital technologies on education in Uzbekistan, this article reviews government policies and reports, academic literature, and research by international organizations. Key sources include a 2020 OECD review of education in Uzbekistan [2], World Bank study on the digital transformation of education in Europe and Central Asia [3], and UNESCO report on leveraging ICT to achieve Education 2030 [4].

The article also examines national ICT in education policies and initiatives in Uzbekistan, such as the e-government and "Digital Uzbekistan 2030" strategies [5], as well as the experience of flagship digital education projects like the IT Park's "One Million Uzbek Coders" program [6]. Additionally, it draws insights from case studies of technology-enhanced teaching and learning at selected schools and universities in Uzbekistan.

RESULTS

The review finds that Uzbekistan has made significant strides in expanding access to digital technologies in education. The government has invested in equipping schools with computers, interactive whiteboards and internet connectivity, resulting in a learner-to-computer ratio of 10:1 in 2020, on par with the Europe and Central Asia average [3]. Uzbekistan has also developed a national online learning platform with over 5,000 video lessons and introduced coding into the secondary school curriculum [5].

At the higher education level, most universities in Uzbekistan now offer blended or fully online courses using learning management systems. Initiatives

like the Ministry of Higher Education's "Digital University" program are digitizing educational content, establishing multimedia centers and training faculty in digital pedagogy [2].

However, the digital transformation of education in Uzbekistan still faces significant challenges. A digital divide persists, with schools in rural areas often lacking sufficient ICT infrastructure and internet connectivity [6]. Teachers need more training and support to effectively integrate digital tools into their practice. There are also concerns about the quality and relevance of some digital educational content.

ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

The increased use of digital technologies in education in Uzbekistan is fundamentally changing how students learn and teachers teach. Digital tools enable access to a wealth of educational content beyond the textbook, support interactive and multimedia learning, facilitate personalized and adaptive instruction, and foster digital skills [4]. This shift aligns with global trends towards learner-centered and lifelong learning models [1].

However, realizing the potential benefits of digital education requires more than just providing devices and connectivity. It requires thoughtful integration of technology into curricula and practice, guided by sound pedagogy and with adequate teacher capacity building [7]. Ensuring equitable access and digital inclusion is also critical to avoid exacerbating existing educational disparities [3].

Uzbekistan's experience with remote learning during the COVID-19 pandemic further exposed these issues. While the government and educational institutions made valiant efforts to roll out online learning, many students lacked devices and internet access at home. Teachers also struggled to adapt to digital instruction with limited prior training [4].

The pandemic also highlighted the limitations of fully online education and the enduring importance of face-to-face interaction and socialization for learning and development [8]. As schools and universities in Uzbekistan reopen, the focus should be on blended learning approaches that strategically combine the strengths of in-person and digital learning.

CONCLUSIONS

This article illustrates the growing role and transformative potential impact of digital technologies on education in Uzbekistan. From expanding access to learning to enabling innovative pedagogies to fostering 21st century skills,

digital technologies offer immense opportunities to enhance educational quality, relevance and equity.

However, for Uzbekistan to fully harness the power of digital education, strategic policies and investments are needed. Priorities include expanding ICT infrastructure and connectivity, especially in underserved areas; providing teachers with training and support to integrate digital tools; developing high-quality, localized digital content; and promoting digital literacy and citizenship skills.

Successful digital transformation of education in Uzbekistan will also require multi-stakeholder collaboration among government, educational institutions, the private sector, civil society and international partners. Critically, digital technologies should not be seen as a silver bullet, but rather as tools to enhance and transform existing educational practices towards more active, personalized, inclusive and lifelong learning.

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